

ISic000909

Epitaph of Daphros

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa,system

Autopsy

None

Last Change

2021-06-20 - Jonathan Prag edited file from available published data and photograph

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found during exploration of the (Rotonda di Adelfia) in June 1872

Coordinates

37.0767995, 15.2848558

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 47

Physical Description

A marble plaque, damaged / roughly cut on all sides, but seemingly inscribed subsequent to any such cutting.

Dimensions

Height 17 cm

Width 22 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Text on two lines, with final letter of line 1 squeezed in small before the broken edge of the stone; two birds and christian monograms fill the space below.

Execution

Letter Forms

Moderately neat and regular letters, cut with a broad groove rather than v-cut, without serifs, but with extensions to tops of some letters (alpha, delta). alpha has broken bar; epsilon is lunate; kappa has full length arms; omicron is full size; rho has small almost closed eye; sigma is lunate but rectilinear; phi is circular with extended vertical; omega (in symbols below) is lunate.

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐνθάδε κείτε
2. Δάφρος □
3. σ□ω(τήρ)

Apparatus

Text after Orsi and photograph
Carini, Kaibel: ΔΑΦΡΟΕ

Translation (en)

Here lies Daphros

Commentary

The form Daphros is not otherwise attested, and Kaibel speculates that Daphnos was intended (although Kaibel, following Carini, actually read Daphroe, which is also unparalleled). The combination of sigma, staurogram, omega between the two doves in the third line presumably signifies 'soter', 'saviour'. Kaibel simply reproduces Carini's text, without included reference to the symbols on the stone, which Carini did report (overleaf on p.34). Orsi transcribed the text and its symbols accurately in his *taccuini* in 1888.

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Photo Museo Arch. Reg. P. Orsi (2012), Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014